

**2001
GOVERNOR'S CONFERENCE
ON THE MANAGEMENT
OF THE
ILLINOIS RIVER SYSTEM**

The Illinois River:
Partnerships for Progress,
Restoration, and
Preservation

Proceedings

Eighth Biennial Conference
October 2-4, 2001
Holiday Inn City Centre
Peoria, Illinois

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INTRODUCTION

Driven by ongoing problems of non-point source pollution and decline of aquatic ecosystems, the 1990's witnessed a rapid development of watershed-scale planning initiatives. Various called "place-based," "community-led," "locally-led," "integrated watershed management," or other similar terms, these initiatives now number over 1000 and are growing rapidly throughout the nation. Nevertheless, these initiatives face numerous obstacles, more social than hydrologic, in achieving improved water quality and aquatic ecosystems, or other natural resource goals that planning groups or the Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Total Maximum Daily Load (TMDL) program may identify (Wescoat, 1997). In particular, water resources and land-use planning in multiple-owner, largely private watersheds has been fragmented and subject to a variety of forces originating both within and outside the watershed (see for example Viessman, 1990; Rogers, 1993). Watersheds do not normally constitute formal, organized political jurisdictions; hence resource planning groups face the challenge of acquiring political legitimacy and legal authority. Deyle (1995) observes that the fragmented decision making that is typical of watershed management constitutes an "organized anarchy" where the involvement of stakeholders is fluid and goals and the means of achieving them are poorly specified, thus too often producing the "pet" solutions of agents who are only temporarily cooperating to address a particular water resources problem. Our work focuses on the watershed planning process.

The purpose of this multi-disciplinary research is to improve our understanding of how the socioeconomic driving forces external and internal to multiple-ownership watersheds influence and restrict the decision making processes of land-use managers and local watershed management institutions. Further, we are building a spatial decision support system (SDSS) to trace the ramifications of these decisions through the watershed ecosystem. This modeling tool will be able to target those positions within the watershed where land-use change is most likely to occur, as well as those where it would have the greatest positive or negative effect on water quality and aquatic ecosystems. The product will be a generalizable framework for watershed management in private-land watersheds. The research focuses on the Cache River of southernmost Illinois as a case study.

Study Area

The Cache River watershed encompasses 1,944 km² of southern Illinois near the confluence of the Mississippi and Ohio Rivers. The watershed has diverse ecological resources and unique natural communities, including bald cypress (*Taxodium distichum* L. Rich.) – water tupelo (*Nyssa aquatica* L.) swamps at the northern edge of their range and other forested wetlands. At least 100 state threatened or endangered plant and animal species are known within the watershed (USFWS 1990). The Cache River region also supports unique ecological communities and 10 globally rare or endangered species. For these reasons, the Cache River Bioreserve was designated by The Nature Conservancy (TNC) and parts of the Cache River watershed were incorporated in the Cypress Creek National Wildlife Refuge.

The ecological integrity of the Cache River ecosystem is threatened by: (1) loss and fragmentation of natural habitats as a result of agricultural activities and timber harvest; (2) dramatically altered hydrologic systems caused by drainage, channelization, and other modifications; (3) sediment deposition in wetlands causing deterioration of water quality and alteration of habitat conditions in Buttonland Swamp; and (4) land use and economic activities that are incompatible with long-term maintenance of ecological functions. Moreover, the

predominantly rural 5-county area has an impoverished economy with minimal infrastructure and weak linkages to the surrounding region which make it sensitive to the cost and benefits of habitat restoration and protection in the Cache River region.

In addition to its scientific importance, the findings and conclusions of this research can be used by watershed planning groups in the watershed, (e.g., the Cache River Watershed Resource Planning Committee (RPC), Local Partnership Councils through C2000) as a basis for developing integrated resource management plans. The RPC was an EPA-funded initiative, sponsored by TNC and the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), involving twenty-five citizens who developed a long range plan for the use of land and water resources in the watershed (Illinois Dept. of Conservation, 1992). In addition to the citizen-based planning committee, there was a 20-member technical committee comprised of representatives from public and private agencies (e.g., Illinois EPA, US Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS), US Forest Service, NRCS, Illinois Dept. of Natural Resources (IDNR), US Army Corps of Engineers, and Southern Illinois University Carbondale that functioned as a "research arm" of the RPC.

To be successful, such a planning process requires information that merges ecological constraints with economic data in a framework relevant for farm level and regional analysis and decision making. Over a period of almost 24 months, the RPC identified a number of paramount natural resource concerns for the watershed and the technical committee developed a range of alternatives for dealing with each concern (RPC, 1995). These alternatives were not without controversy, reflecting the diversity of the RPC membership. For watershed planning to be successful, strategies must be developed that permit the recommending of a set of alternatives acceptable to land owners/managers and residents of the watershed, while providing the necessary ecological benefits to maintain the viability of the endangered ecosystem. Thus the Cache River watershed represents a unique opportunity to study the social dynamics of watershed management in a multiple-owner watershed that is undergoing substantial ecological restoration.

Methodologies, Results, and Discussion—A Work in Progress

Through a coordinated process, the research team working as individual members, as small working groups, and as a group of the whole has been exploring a number of areas related to watershed planning. For this paper, we will briefly summarize the ongoing work related to the legal framework informing watershed planning in Illinois, the factors related to the legitimacy of the planning process and the resulting plan, and the development of tools for integrated watershed planning integrating socio-economic and ecological factors. Since the research is still very much ongoing, the material presented here should be seen as preliminary and indicative of what we are learning and might well be relevant to watershed planning in the Illinois River basin.

As part of the research, a thorough review was made of federal and state statutes "informing" or structuring watershed planning. We have a plethora of federal and Illinois laws that impact agriculture and by extension planning activity within watersheds. We have identified 25 different laws that potentially have a role, (e.g., water and air quality, solid and hazardous waste, pesticide and fertilizer application, soil conservation and farm bill legislation, etc). The multi-jurisdictional nature of these laws and their attendant regulations and rules result in a fractured system of media specific laws on one hand, (e.g., water, air, and soil/land) and action specific laws, (e.g. pesticide and fertilizer application) on the other, producing overlap and complexity. In addition, there are no laws specific to the processes of watershed planning and the implementation of resulting plans.

The fractured nature of the regulatory environment may well explain why the local population apparently does not have a grasp on the laws that affect them. Secondly, this inconsistent and complex legal environment will make the sort of reform necessary to facilitate watershed planning more difficult. Thirdly, the present system leaves us without a holistic law governing watershed management and informing the planning process. We hypothesize that this lack of a unified watershed law compromises legitimacy of the planning process, the resulting plans, and the results achieved on the landscape.

As part of the research, the research team identified 30 individuals who were significant players in the recently completed watershed planning process in the Cache River watershed. We conducted open-ended interviews with 27 of these key people. They were drawn from the three major groups involved in the planning process: 14 personnel from the Technical Committee (TC) and associated governmental agencies, 11 members of the RPC who were landowners in the watershed, and two local activists who were not members of the RPC but who had been involved in

watershed issues for many years.

The interview questions covered aspects of their personal lives, their recollections and assessments of the functioning of the RPC, their knowledge of the roles of various groups and regulations relevant to the Cache watershed, their recommendations to other watershed planning groups, and their judgment of the major problems currently facing the Cache River region. The 1-2 hour interviews were transcribed and coded. The coding was used both as a discovery mechanism and as an analytic tool. We used a set of pre-defined categories to code for personal data and data concerning group processes. We used a more open-ended set of analytic categories to permit interpretation of the specific data collected in the interviews. These categories included legitimacy, judgments concerning specific aspects of the data (e.g., group processes, roles of different personnel and agencies, land acquisition by agencies), recommendations, articulation of interests, social resource flows, gender and other implicit divisions or distinctions in perceptions, perceptions of salience of insider/outsider distinctions, and other categories that were discovered through the coding process. From this we derived a streamlined set of seven categories that were used to guide the development of focus group questions.

Based on the interviews and literature review, we have developed a set of preliminary findings that will help to guide the remainder of the research. Our primary questions involved how (and if) watershed planning becomes legitimate and thereby capable of shaping the actions of individuals as they interact with each other and with the landscape of the watershed. This involved discovering key actors within the watershed and determining how these actors develop their authority and legitimacy. The preliminary findings, based on initial analysis of the interviews, are:

(1) Outcome of the process: The Watershed Plan coming from the RPC provides local agency personnel with legitimacy in their requests for support from higher levels of their agencies for programs they wish to implement. Virtually all agency (NRCS, FWS, IDNR) personnel noted that the "grassroots" planning process and resultant plan provided them with a powerful basis for arguing for support for programs they initiated locally.

(2) Perceptions of the planning process: The internal dynamics of the planning process were perceived very differently by members of the RPC (all local "stakeholders") and members of the TC (agency personnel and other technical experts). The initial groundrules for the planning process, instituted by the NRCS, established distinct roles for the RPC and the TC: members of the Technical Committee were to provide technical information only and were not to participate in the actual discussions and decision-making processes. TC members were keenly aware of the proscription on their active participation, while the members of the RPC had no practical knowledge of this proscription and perceived the TC members as fully participant. Nonetheless, most members of the RPC felt they had substantially contributed to the final plan, and did not feel overwhelmed by members of the TC.

(3) Resource mobilization: The social resources on which different groups and individuals drew differed considerably. The various agencies, transparently, derived their capacity to act from the financial and organizational capacity of their governmental and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs). There appeared to be a significant difference in the resources mobilized by farmers and by environmentalists as they pursued their often conflicting aims regarding use of watershed lands. They had recourse to different agencies (farmers: Illinois and US Departments of Agriculture, especially the NRCS; environmentalists: EPA, FWS, IDNR); different NGOs (farmers: Farm Bureau; environmentalists: TNC, Sierra Club, Audubon Society); and different branches of government (farmers: local drainage districts, perhaps other local governing bodies, including Soil and Water Conservation Districts; environmentalists, especially through the agency of TNC, federal and state executive personnel.) Both groups sought support from elected officials, and lobbied them directly and through their representative organizations. The Corps of Engineers seemed to operate in an arena in which local actors could only indirectly influence their decision-making.

(4) Local power structures: The environmental or resource use issues that created political divisions within the Cache River watershed exposed significant aspects of the structuring of local power. Despite the watershed's relatively small size, it embraces five counties and

three discrete orderings of power: In the uplands, political, economic, and social power appear quite diffuse, based on relatively small landholdings and relatively diversified economies. In the eastern regions, opened to cultivation in the twentieth century by the building of the Post Creek Cut Off, relatively large-scale farmers operate in a relatively decentralized political system. In the southwestern counties, a history of cotton production and association with the Mississippi River appears to have promoted a political and economic system dominated by a few powerful families. These regional differences mitigate against coherent regional planning, and create the conditions in which farmers and other actors make highly localized judgments about the costs and benefits of specific policies for watershed management. That is, watersheds do not necessarily define socially meaningful regions.

(5) The planning process, which restricted its membership to "stakeholders" defined as property-owners within the watershed, may have defined its constituency too narrowly. The degree to which the plan attains broader legitimacy, and has the ability to influence local governing policies, may have been limited by the nature of the representatives. This tentative finding was suggested by the interviews with key informants and has been supported by findings from the focus groups.

Building on information gained through the key informant interviews, focus groups were organized to investigate local knowledge and perceptions within the Cache River region. Focus groups were held with three groups: elected officials, rural and small town residents, and farmers (not on the RPC). Our approach followed the suggested focus group format (see The Focus Group Kit. Morgan and Krueger, 1998, Sage Publications). Groups consisted of 3 to 11 people with similar backgrounds (identified by residence or occupation as noted). For each focus group, it was necessary to identify participants through specific methods. Public officials were identified through public documents. Rural and small town residents were identified through a random sample of telephone numbers, listed in the telephone book by identified towns within the watershed. Farmers were identified by NRCS District Conservationists, and represented the counties in the watershed.

Once these samples were identified, potential participants were contacted by telephone and asked to attend a specific focus group session. Participants received \$20 for taking part in a session. Focus group meetings lasted 2 hours, during which participants were asked a set of 12 questions that were carefully worded to illicit discussion on natural resource topics. During the focus group sessions, key points were written on a large flip chart; this allowed participants to refer back to and elaborate on important topics. The sessions were also tape-recorded and transcribed by a professional stenographer. The full text provides researchers with rich contextual information from each group, while the flip chart provides a concise overview of each focus groups' important discussion points.

The purpose of these social focus groups was to investigate peoples' opinions on natural resource and watershed issues in the Cache River watershed. Thus we sought to learn participants' views on what issues are important, how they gain information, and what they know about the existing planning process. Further, we investigated local awareness of watershed concepts and issues of trust and legitimacy. The questions asked of each groups are listed below:

1. *opening*: Please tell us your name, where you live, and what you like best about living and working in southern Illinois.
- 2a. *introductory*: I'd like you to take a moment and make a list of the environmental or natural resource issues in the Cache River area that are important to you. (Make a list on a flip-chart.)
 - 2b. *follow-up*: Where do you get information about any of these issues?
 - 2c. *follow-up*: When making decisions about how to manage your land or whether to support a particular proposal, what information would you use and trust?
 - 2d. *follow-up*: When referring to these issues, I used both the term "environmental" and "natural resource." Do you see a difference between the two?
3. *transition*: Now, let's turn our attention to the term "watershed." How would you describe a "watershed"?

4. *key:* What activities dealing with environmental or natural resources are you aware of in the Cache River watershed and who is involved?
- 5a. *key:* When developing an action plan for dealing with the issues listed here (point to our flip chart) for the Cache River watershed, what would it take for you to feel comfortable with that plan?
- 5b. *follow-up:* Who should participate in that planning process?
6. *key:* Does an area like a watershed require an administrative or political structure?
- 7a. *key:* What rules or regulations that pertain to water and land use management are you aware of?
- 7b. *follow-up:* Do you think these are useful regulations?
- 7c. *follow-up:* How do you stay informed about these legal matters?

Offer a short (2-3 minute) oral summary of the focus group session.

8. *summary:* How well does that capture what was said here?
9. *final:* Is there anything that we should have talked about but didn't?
10. *(for first group only):* This is the first in a series of groups that we are doing. Do you have any advice on how we can improve a session like this?

The following key findings were discovered through the focus group sessions. First, important similarities were found among the three groups that indicate some common general perceptions within the watershed. There was little public awareness of the two years of public meetings held by the Resource Planning Committee in 1993-94. A handful of people who did know of the meetings expressed mostly negative opinions, as they doubted whether anything had really been accomplished. But the majority of focus group participants indicated that they were not familiar with any citizen-based groups in the watershed. In addition to this void in terms of citizen involvement, many focus group participants were unaware of the various government agencies and NGOs active in the Cache watershed. Notably, the FWS, the IDNR, and TNC have been key players in Cache wetland and regional land management for more than 20 years. Some participants, particularly the farmers, knew there were government agencies active in land acquisition, but did not know which agencies and for what purpose. Another interesting similarity, and one that will have an impact on the wording of the future telephone survey, is how people perceive "environmental" versus "natural resources." Although a few people said the terms were interchangeable, most participants noted that "environment" indicates more preservationist goals, "treehuggers" and even a negative control over resources. The term "natural resources," on the other hand, is perceived as specific resources such as water, trees, coal, oil, etc. and the use of these resources.

Second, findings from the three focus groups indicate how different perceptions are held by the three types of Cache residents. For example the groups have very different ideas about regional environmental concerns. When asked to identify the key environmental issues in the region, public officials mentioned water contamination, pollution, and federal mandates; rural residents noted hunting, fishing, tourism, and preservation; while farmers stated that property rights, drainage, and the decline of agriculture were key issues among others.

Similarly, the groups varied in their ability to define a watershed, which indicates very different levels of understanding about their local environment. While the public officials and residents had vague notions about what a watershed is, (i.e., water supply or water flow), the farmers had a clear understanding of a watershed. The farmer focus group provided a very clear and accurate definition: the area of land that drains to a single point or stream. Perhaps this indicates that farmers have greater understanding of the interconnected nature of water quality and use throughout the region. As a follow up question, we investigated whether these local people felt there was a need to have some type of watershed-level administration. The public officials believe that yes, this could be helpful in joining together all the various groups and regulations. The residents believe that a watershed administration might be useful, but only if it was based on local input. The farmers felt that such administration was not necessary; that the region did not need "more government."

Related to watershed administration, the groups were questioned about their knowledge of current regulations in the area. Public officials noted that there were many water quality regulations; residents knew about pollution regulations and use rules (for fishing, parks, hunting,

etc.); and farmers noted there is substantial regulation of wetland drainage, land clearing and agricultural chemical applications.

Finally, the groups varied in terms of their use of information sources and their perceptions of what makes resource planning acceptable. Public officials tend to rely on government agencies and job experience; residents rely on friends and park rangers; while farmers turn to Farm Bureau and agricultural agencies, such as NRCS, for their information. In terms of accepting any watershed-based plan, the three groups indicated various justifications: officials stated that such a plan must clearly describe why it is necessary; residents noted that the planning process must include public meetings; and farmers stated that planning must include farmer input and allow "zero land acquisition." This indicates that previous planning activities in the watershed, although not clearly articulated in other questions, are viewed negatively by the farmers. This includes the creation of the Cypress Creek National Wildlife Refuge and land purchases by TNC.

At the conclusion of each focus group, the participants were asked to provide additional comments. The three groups each elaborated on unique and varying points. First, the public officials noted that federal mandates often cost local people a great deal, but do not allow local input. Second, the rural and small town residents felt that southern Illinois needs more recreational opportunities, particularly camping sites; and that the government should do a better job of land management in the region. Third, the farmers believe that the public should be educated about agriculture; that people blame farmers for environmental problems and do not understand that farmers are "good environmentalists."

In conclusion, findings from these focus groups indicate that local people in the Cache watershed are unaware of the previous and on-going planning efforts in the region. People generally do not know about the agencies and groups active in the region. There is variation, however, among public officials, residents, and farmers as to their knowledge and perceptions of environmental issues, watershed concepts, need for watershed administration, knowledge of environmental regulations, sources of information used, and reasons for accepting watershed planning.

The development and refinement of an SDSS has continued as part of the project. The goal is to have an SDSS that will show the economic and environmental consequences of different policy scenarios designed to enhance environmental quality. Watershed planners would then be able to develop a number of scenarios and see their economic consequences and the implications for the watershed's landscape. Two approaches have been pursued in this effort:

- (1) spatially distributed linear programming designed to find the land uses maximizing the returns to management and fixed resources while meeting environmental constraints. The resulting land uses are then used as input in programs designed to simulate nonpoint-source pollution (e.g., AGNPS).

- (2) genetic algorithm (GA) based analytical tools to handle the multiple objectives involved in watershed planning.

Spatial decision support systems are designed to help decision-makers explore the bounds of geographical problems through the generation and evaluation of alternative solutions. An SDSS links several spatially explicit models together so that the economic context of farm management decisions and practices can be combined with the ecologic and hydrologic repercussions of farm management practices. That is, farmers strive to maximize their goals (e.g., profit) within the constraints of available technology and public policy (e.g., US Dept. of Agriculture (USDA) programs) that express both social and environmental objectives. Thus, land use decisions manifest across the landscape in particular patterns of land use/land cover and affect ecosystem processes and outputs. Put another way, farmer managers' decisions have consequences beyond those that are socioeconomic. Landscape structure, function, and change, fundamental characteristics that are relevant to landscape ecology (Turner 1989), are affected. An SDSS provides a means for combining economic and geomorphic/hydrologic modeling to assess both the social and ecologic impacts of land management practices.

Here we have developed SDSS tools to help in the analysis of the Cache River watershed. The first of these tools is designed to help decision-makers understand the economic impact of alternative environmental regulations designed to reduce nonpoint source pollution. At the heart of this system is a linear programming optimization model that constructs a landscape to maximize economic return from agricultural production subject to user specified environmental and economic

constraints. This model operates at the farm level. The basin wide environmental implications of these constraints are evaluated using the Agricultural Nonpoint Source (AGNPS) pollution model. We constructed a link between a spatially-distributed version of a linear programming farm management model (referred to here as GEOLP) to the AGNPS pollution model via a commonly available geographic information system (GIS) software package (ArcView GIS 3.1 produced by the ESRI (1996)).

GEOLP is linked to GIS software via Avenue scripts and allows the user to model a set of farms in a watershed as an economic system comprised of independent decision-makers. An Avenue script sequentially selects individual farms from a digital map of all farms in a watershed and develops the linear programming input file for each farm using associated spatial (e.g., watershed-level digital soil maps that record productivity and erodibility by crop, tillage practice and soil type) and aspatial data relevant to specific farms and the agricultural economy (e.g., labor and machinery costs and availability constraints). Each GEOLP output file produced through this process captures the optimal tillage and cropping land cover pattern for a particular farm, the income generated from the land cover, and the estimated soil loss by soil type based on the Universal Soil Loss Equation (Wischmeier and Smith 1978). This information is generated given user-defined constraints. Aggregating across farms provides data for the entire watershed.

AGNPS is an event based, distributed parameter model developed by the USDA Agricultural Research Service in cooperation with the Minnesota Pollution Control Agency and the Natural Resource Conservation Service (Young et al., 1989, 1994). AGNPS models hydrology, erosion, and the transport of sediment and chemicals through a watershed. AGNPS is also capable of simulating sediment yield from gullies, input of water-soluble nutrients, and the impact of runoff from animal feedlots on in-stream chemical oxygen demand. In the hydrology module of the program, runoff volume and peak flow at the outlet of the watershed are calculated. The erosion module calculates total upland erosion and total channel erosion. Chemical transport is measured in terms of soluble and sediment-attached pollutants. A grid-based data structure is used to capture spatial heterogeneity. AGNPS input files are generated using the land-cover maps produced by GEOLP and other GIS datasets (e.g., digital elevation model (for topography) and soil coverage), see Figure 1.

The Big Creek (part of the IDNR Pilot Watershed Program) and Cypress Creek watersheds, tributaries of the Cache River, were used to implement the SDSS. Special tabulations of returns from the 1987 and 1992 Censuses of Agriculture for farms in the Cache River, resulted in land-use statistics required as part of the necessary economic input. In particular, farm size frequency distributions (e.g., acres operated), guided the development of farms modeled to maximize economic returns, defined as gross margin (i.e., the return to the farmer's management and the capital invested in the business). Utilizing a clustering routine available in ARC/INFO, the Big Creek landscape was allocated into 96 farming units, and the Cypress Creek landscape was allocated into 93 farms. That is, continuous blocks of land were grouped to create farms whose boundaries differ from the boundaries of actual farms. The average acreage of these farms was 245 acres (range of 56 to 716 acres). In 1992, the actual average Cache farm size was 256 acres.

Crop type, tillage practice, and timing of farm activities are among the economic decision variables considered by GEOLP. Crop types include corn, soybean, wheat, double crop soybean/wheat and alfalfa. A livestock (calf-cow) operation was also allowed. Conventional, conservation, and no-till farming practices comprise the set of alternative tillage practices. The Conservation Reserve Program (CRP), a USDA program that pays rent to farmers to set aside their arable but highly erodible land, was also considered as an "activity". In addition some of the land was forced into idle use activities to reflect the approximate 20% of non-forested idle Cache lands.

For this analysis we focused our investigation on the different levels of T required by the "T by 2000" mandate, and the incorporation of filter strips into the landscape. One benefit of using a GIS is the ability to locate spatially explicit watershed activities and characteristics. For example, in Figure 2, the left-hand side of the figure presents the spatial distribution of land cover for Big Creek assuming farmers face ten-year average commodity prices, no CRP, and no constraints on soil loss. The right-hand side presents the implications for sediment yield at various points along the Big Creek drainage network and at the mouth of Big Creek assuming the land cover on the left and a 1.5 inch rain event. The figure also indicates what happens to sediment yield assuming farmers face a soil loss constraint of "T" per acre and there is a CRP. Figure 3 shows how the land cover changes as farmers respond to the new soil loss constraint of "T" and the availability of the CRP. However, the implications of the change in land cover in terms of farm

income are not evenly distributed across the watershed. Figure 4, illustrates how the impacts on farm income are unevenly distributed across the landscape as well as demonstrating how the SDSS can be used to identify areas in the watershed that might bear a significant portion of the costs associated with policies designed to achieve environmental goals.

To enhance the SDSS, a genetic algorithm (GA) (see Figure 5) has been developed and integrated with USDA's comprehensive watershed simulation model known as Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) (Arnold et al., 1998). This single objective evaluation model is capable of evaluating the optimal land use distribution across a watershed to minimize sediment yield. Ultimately, however, land use management decisions should not only account for environmental impacts of erosion, but should also integrate the feasibility of the designed policy from the socioeconomic perspective.

With regard to an agricultural watershed with multiple landowners, a likely stakeholder concern may be the economic benefit that s/he may generate from her/his farm. A systematic method of including this individual owner's perspective into a decision support system is very crucial for successful implementation of the policy. To address this critical socioeconomic factor, a multiobjective evaluation technique that operates on a farm scale and that integrates both economic and environmental objectives has been developed. In this way, all stakeholders in the watershed contribute to the common goal of reducing adverse impacts of erosion from their commonly owned watershed, while preserving their private goals of maximizing farm income. The multiobjective model is designed to yield the land use patterns that simultaneously minimize sediment yield and maximize net farm-level profits from a watershed.

The particular approach used here interfaces SWAT with a genetic algorithm based multiobjective global search strategy known as Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm (SPEA) (Zitzler and Thiele, 1999) to locate non-dominated Pareto optimal solutions (see Figure 6). Both the single objective and multiobjective models have been tested using the Big Creek watershed and have demonstrated a capability to address their respective objectives. However, both models were found to be computationally intensive, primarily as a result of required, repeated application of the hydrologic model (SWAT). In efforts to resolve this problem, which ultimately may hamper practical utility of these important watershed decision support tools, the capability of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) in replacing and mimicking SWAT has been explored. A multilayer feed-forward ANN was trained to approximate estimates of sediment yield and net economic profit that SWAT provides as a result of implementing various land use types and management combinations over a decision horizon. The training was accomplished by using a hybrid of evolutionary programming and a back propagation algorithm to alleviate shortcomings of traditional ANN training approaches. The training technique was found to be highly effective in reproducing SWAT's estimates. The ANN was then used to replace SWAT in the multiobjective decision support tool. The replacement has significantly reduced the CPU time required for generation of optimal landscapes by approximately 75 percent.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Our ongoing research in the Cache River watershed suggests that there are a number of concerns of which individuals and agencies involved with watershed planning in the Illinois River watershed need to be aware. First, the lack of legislation informing watershed planning and the resulting plans can result in those activities lacking legitimacy in the eyes of the residents of the watershed. Nor can agency personnel assume that an apparently open, public process will result in a plan that residents of the watershed are aware of or assent to. How watershed planning activities and resulting plans acquire legitimacy in the eyes of landowners and managers as well as nonfarm residents is an issue that needs to be understood and addressed. A corollary is the need to understand how the mosaic of existing laws, rules, and regulations structures the watershed planning process and the implementation of resulting plans. Second, in the minds of the residents, the concept of "watershed" is not well defined nor does it necessarily correspond to the understanding that agency personnel have. This lack of knowledge and agreement as to what a watershed is can hinder the whole policy thrust of using locally led watershed planning as the primary tool for correcting nonpoint source pollution and ecological restoration. Third, even when planning processes involve public participation and hearings—the RPC held hearings regarding the identification of watershed problems and for presenting the resulting plan, there is no guarantee that the wider community in the watershed will be aware of the results. Fourth, the development of SDSSs to incorporate

multiple objectives along with the spatial presentation of results are powerful tools for assessing the distribution of "benefits" and "costs" resulting from alternative options designed to address the needs of the watershed.

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Figure 1: Development of GEOLP and AGNPS through Farm Based Land Cover

Figure 2: Land use and resulting sediment yield: Big Creek Watershed

Figure 3: Policy effect on land use: Big Creek Watershed

Figure 4: Policy effect on farm income: Big Creek Watershed

Figure 5: Logic of the GA

Figure 6: Trade-off between non-point source pollution and farm profitability

